

Advancing and facilitating the use of RCM data in climate impacts research

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Abstract— The use of Regional Climate Model (RCM) output for climate impacts research is a promising cross-cutting approach with mutual benefits for both, the climate modeling and the climate impacts communities. However, so far this scientific potential is by far not fully tapped. Here, we aim at identifying the main hurdles and challenges associated with the use of RCM data in fields of climate impacts and adaptation research and discuss strategies to overcome them.

Index Terms—Regional Climate Model (RCM), impacts research, adaption, scientific collaboration between the disciplines

1 Introduction

Regional Climate Models (RCMs) are important tools to provide quantitative, physically consistent estimates of regional climate change. Therefore, RCM output is increasingly used as input for regional and local climate impacts models. During the past years, several comprehensive international efforts that aim at providing RCM data for climate impacts research have been implemented, e.g. ENSEMBLES (van der Linden and Mitchell, 2009), NARCCAP (Mearns et al. 2009) or CORDEX (Giorgi et al. 2009). Accordingly, it is a matter of mutual interest of the climate modeling and climate impacts communities that this expensively acquired RCM output is used efficiently for application in impacts studies.

It is thus remarkable that the scientific potential associated with the use of RCM output is only partly tapped so far. Just as the data flow between climate models and impacts models is usually unidirectional, there appears only little feedback from impacts modelers or “end users” back to the climate modeling community. Moreover, only comparatively few impacts scientists are working directly with raw RCM output, and scientific teams that include researchers from both communities are still rare, as can be deduced from the author lists of many conference contributions and publications.

Motivated by this context, a three-day workshop on ‘Regional climate model data for climate impacts research’ has been jointly organized in February 2013 by the project TEMPS (‘The Evolution of Mountain Permafrost in Switzerland’; a *Sinergia* programme of the Swiss National Science Founda-

tion) and the Center for Climate Systems Modeling of ETH Zurich (C2SM). The workshop's objective was to bring together researchers from various impacts disciplines to provide basic training for the handling, pre-processing and evaluation of RCM generated data, and to identify and discuss challenges and hurdles that impede their application for climate change impacts studies. 24 impacts researcher from different fields such as glaciology, hydrology, agriculture, ecology, biology, meteorology and climatology participated in the workshop. Most of the participants had already used RCM output or plan to use it for future work. Actual and planned uses range from applying raw RCM output to utilizing sophisticated climate scenario products, and cover the whole spectrum of spatial and temporal scales (from 3-hourly to decadal mean) as well as a great number of available variables. This article summarizes some of the main outcomes of the workshop, complemented by experiences collected by the authors over the past years. In this regard, the intention of the present article is (i) to provide an overview and an analysis of the barriers that impede the adoption of RCM simulation results by impacts researchers, and (ii) to initiate the discussion on how to improve communication and collaboration between the communities in order to tap the full potential of climate model data in general and of RCM data in particular.

2 Basic Challenges

2.1 The heterogeneity of the impacts community

The term 'climate impacts research' suggests a well-defined research direction and a community with clear objectives, a common methodological toolbox, and well-defined input data needs. However, the climate impacts community is in fact a highly heterogeneous group that includes natural and social scientists, economists and decision makers and which correspondingly exhibits a rich diversity of research objectives, methods and data requirements (Fig. 1). A scientifically oriented user might for example utilize RCM output to drive a model of ground surface temperature at a number of specific permafrost sites to enhance the understanding of this specific process (e.g. Salzmann et al. 2007, Scherler et al. 2013). Or an economist might want to use gridded RCM output that covers a national economy to derive the best estimate of an index variable, such as heating degree days, as input to an economic integrated assessment model (e.g. Gonseth and Vielle, 2012).

This broad range of applications in concert with an often sub-optimal understanding of the characteristics of RCM output makes it difficult for the impacts community to specify simple, clear, and unambiguous common requirements for the data input to be provided by the climate modelers. Those, in turn, often lack the expertise in the specific fields of impacts research that would be necessary to advise the 'end users' in that regard. These deficits form a major impediment for the use of

climate model output in impacts research.

Figure 1: Context and current data delivery procedures of using climate model output for subsequent application in impacts and adaptation research. Black arrows indicate data/information transfer.

2.2 Technical issues

The data formats, software tools and conceptual approaches for data representation and modeling used by impacts researcher can vitally differ from those used by climate modelers. For example the NetCDF data format used to represent gridded, time dependent climate datasets differs significantly from what many impacts researchers are used to work with, e.g. ASCII formatted data for station (point) climate data or special vector data formats used in Geographic Information Systems. As a consequence, processing (raw) climate model output into a shape ready to be digested by impact modelers' tools often requires a great initial effort.

The option of using post-processed RCM data in form of readily available scenario products, such as the Swiss Climate Change Scenarios (CH2011, 2011), is thus attractive for many impacts researcher. However, it remains to be discussed whether this approach is flexible enough to be recommended as a general strategy (see section 4).

2.3 The 'one-directional data-delivery' procedure

Currently, the modus operandi of how RCM data is provided for further use in impacts research is a one-way process from the climate modeling community to the impacts community. Usually, there is no feedback channel which would provide 'end users' with an opportunity to voice their specific requirements, report problems, or obtain in-depth information, for example regarding the data's exact meaning, its suitability for specific applications, or the associated uncertainties. Thus, potentially valuable information for both communities and an opportunity for stimulating scientific exchange are lost.

3 Analyses of current hurdles faced by the impacts modeler

It is a challenging task for impacts modelers to assess the characteristics of RCM output. This includes the representativeness of gridded data, the uncertainties inherent in the climate model output, and the identification, correction and extrapolation of model biases. Climate model validation exercises that are routinely applied by climate modelers, such as the validation over large domains and/or aggregated time periods (monthly, seasonal, 30-year mean, etc.) for main variables such as air temperature and precipitation, are hardly sufficient for regional-to-local scale impacts studies. They require a domain- and process-specific RCM validation that ideally would be carried out in a collaborative effort between climate modeler and impacts researcher.

Many impacts researcher typically work with point data (i.e. climate station). Using gridded data instead (often with a spatial resolution on the order of 20 – 50 km) raises various challenges related to the representativeness of a grid point and respective validation procedures, downscaling techniques, extreme values, and finally the application to regional-to-local scale impacts models. This becomes particularly evident in complex mountain topography (e.g. Kotlarski et al. 2012; Salzmann et al. 2012) but also in remote locations, where appropriate observations for model validation are usually scarce or even lacking. Yet, it is often in such regions where climate model output and re-analysis products become interesting for impacts researchers, because no other data for the past and present are available. Here, collaboration with the climate modeling community is of utmost importance because only an intimate knowledge of model parametrizations, assumptions, inherent and scale-dependent uncertainties, and other dependencies on data reliability and robustness will guard against grave mistakes. Moreover, the performance of RCMs regarding the realism of statistical properties of the simulated time series such as variance, autocorrelation structure, spectral characteristics, or occurrence of extremes is often not clear to many impacts researchers, but fundamental for numerous impacts processes. A particular challenge in that regard is the proper use of the

information contained in multi-model ensemble simulations. Multi-model averages have been shown to be more accurate than single model predictions in many cases (Knutti, 2010 and references therein), but the averaged time series also exhibit less realistic properties, such as reduced variability, which might be important for impacts applications. Model averaging and associated methods are highly technical and present significant obstacles for the non-specialist. While the representativeness of gridded climate model data with respect to local extremes is not clear for the past, it is even more difficult to assess it for future scenarios. Furthermore, particularly in the case of extremes, clarity on the definition of 'extremes' in each community is crucial. Here, the potential for misunderstanding due to the use of different terminologies is obvious.

Associated with the 'point vs. grid' issue is the topic of bias correction and/or further downscaling, here referred to as 'empirical-statistical' approaches. Empirical-statistical downscaling can be applied at different levels of complexity (e.g. Benestad et al. 2008, Maraun et al. 2010). Impacts researcher depend on expert judgments with regard to the potential, the limits, and the optimal choice of the empirical-statistical post-processing of RCM data for their respective applications. Particularly for the more complex approaches, a small community is about to be formed within the recently launched COST Action VALUE (Validating and Integrating Downscaling Methods for Climate Change Research; <http://www.value-cost.eu>).

4 Is there a need for a 'translator community'?

It is obvious that both communities benefit from enhanced collaboration but that also certain efforts are required from both sides.

Although the impacts community is highly diverse and common needs are difficult to formulate, each discipline clearly needs to assess the sensitivities of their specific processes and models with respect to changes in related key climate variables. Knowledge about the particular sensitivities will help to communicate with the climate modelers and to handle the uncertainties of RCM data for impacts research.

With increasing climate model resolution and the constant incorporation of additional and/or improved parameterization schemes, extended process knowledge and expertise outside the field of atmospheric research will become increasingly important for climate model development. Many impacts researcher can provide knowledge and data on such processes and thus are potentially important partners for the climate modeling community.

In general, members from both communities need to invest time and efforts to improve their under-

standing of the concepts and models of each other. This requires participating at dedicated conferences, reading specific literature and publishing jointly. For many community members such an endeavor is not an option, though. Therefore, the concept of a 'translator community', formed by scientists from all involved disciplines, and advance and facilitate collaboration between the communities, needs to be pushed forward. Even though this idea has been entering the discussion at times (e.g. Leung et al. 2003) and scattered efforts exist, the growth of such a community to a well visible and significant size is also hampered in the current scientific setting, where highly specialized research is typically most prestigious. Therefore, explicit stimuli by funding agencies, universities and research institutions, for example through dedicated research programs and chair offers, might tip the scale. Linking these endeavors to current efforts in the field of climate change impacts and adaptation is particularly promising.

Initiatives such as the Swiss Climate Change Scenarios project (CH2011, 2011) might be seen as an alternative to a 'translator community'. Here, vastly post-processed RCM data in form of tailored scenario products were provided to the impacts community. This product, based on the ENSEMBLES set of multi-model GCM-RCM chains (van der Linden et al. 2009), was developed in an elaborate process that stressed the assessment and the communication of uncertainties, limitations and areas of applicability. Such data is highly appreciated for its ease of application by many users, particularly by those outside academia, e.g. consulting companies and government agencies. An important part of the CH2011 scenario development was the intensive discussion between climate modelers and potential end-users in order to identify their specific needs. Public climate scenario initiatives are thus not an alternative to scientific collaboration, but are rather a service for practitioners who don't have the resources for scientific examination. However, the scientific potential associated with the collaborative analyses and use of raw RCM output in climate impacts research, which aims at enhancing the understanding of physical key processes, is certainly not fully tapped by such initiatives.

5 Conclusions

There is a high scientific potential in the use of climate model output in impacts research, with mutual benefits for all involved communities and likely important inputs for the pressing challenges related to climate change impacts and adaptation.

Establishing a dedicated 'translator community' is probably an optimal strategy to advance and facilitate cross-cutting science between climate modeling and impacts research. However, readiness of scientists from all involved disciplines, ideally stimulated by funding agencies and research institutions, are badly needed to give such efforts the required weight in science.

Initiatives such as CH2011 certainly respond to the needs of practice-oriented ‘end users’, but are not an alternative to the enhanced scientific collaboration between research communities.

Furthermore, large programs, such as ENSEMBLES or CORDEX, that provide ‘raw’ RCM output should extensively document the provided model results with metadata that could be useful for impacts modeler, such as known caveats, limits of applicability, biases for certain regions and variables, and known sources and estimated magnitudes of uncertainties. Naming of contact persons for specific questions could also prove very useful.

Finally, it is obvious that not all of the needs formulated by impacts researchers are realizable. Therefore, enhanced collaboration and communication is indispensable to improve mutual understanding towards mutual benefits.

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